

Factors influencing the use of forensic awareness strategies in sexual homicide

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Introduction

According to the *CSI effect* hypothesis, TV shows depicting forensic analyses have influenced the public's attitudes and expectations related to the use of scientific evidence in jury trials (Baskin & Sommers, 2010). Although it is still debated whether or not the *CSI effect* really exists (e.g., Baskin & Sommers, 2010; Beauregard & Martineau, 2018; Chopin & Beauregard, in press; Holmgren & Fordham, 2011; Kim, Barak, & Shelton, 2009; Schweitzer & Saks, 2007; Smith, Patry, & Stinson, 2007; Stinson, Patry, & Smith, 2007; Tyler, 2006), Cole and Dioso-Villa (2007) suggested that the *CSI effect* could be in fact educational for criminals, providing them with new strategies to learn how to avoid police detection as well as an increased sophistication in the commission of their crimes. It is true that despite most criminals not knowing what "DNA" stands for, most, if not all, are aware that it is found at the crime scene, and that it could be used to identify them and ultimately link them to the crime. However, recent studies have shown that not all offenders take actions at the crime scene in order to get rid of forensic evidence – the so-called use of forensic awareness strategies (FAS) (see Beauregard & Martineau, 2018; Chan, 2019; Chopin & Beauregard, in press for a review).

Although the use of FAS is not the only factor responsible for detection avoidance by sexual homicide offenders (SHOs) (see Balemba, Beauregard, & Martineau, 2014; Beauregard & Martineau, 2014, 2018; James & Beauregard, 2018), it is nonetheless interesting from a decision-making perspective to examine this specific component of the modus operandi aimed at avoiding police detection. We argue that the understanding of the crime-commission process requires a consideration of not only the actions taken by SHOs to maximize the payoffs of their crimes but also the strategies adopted to minimize the costs associated with the crime (i.e., being apprehended). Although the first type of actions have

often been investigated (see e.g., Beauregard & Martineau, 2017), the mechanisms surrounding the second type of actions remain unknown. As such, the current study examines the decisions taken by SHOs to either adopt or not FAS as a method to avoid police detection. Specifically, this study seeks to determine which factors of the crime-commission process are associated with a decision to adopt FAS to avoid police detection in sexual homicide (SH) cases. Based on the research on the use of FAS by rapists (see Chopin & Beauregard, in press), we specifically examined the impact of the offender's expertise, the situational aspects of the crime, as well as the crime characteristics to explain the use – or not – of FAS by SHOs. These findings could be important both at a theoretical and practical level, improving our understanding of the crime-commission process adopted by SHOs to avoid detection, while also suggesting practical implications for the police investigation.

Avoiding Police Detection: A Rational Choice Approach

The rational choice approach (Cornish & Clarke, 1986, 1987) provides a theoretical framework to understand how criminals make decisions and proposes that rationality and self-interest are foundational principles of decision-making (Clarke & Cornish, 1985; Piquero & Tibbetts, 2002). This approach states that offenders make decisions to gain more than what it costs to commit the crime (Cornish & Clarke, 1986, 1987). Thus, in following a cost-benefit analysis, the expected benefits should be greater than the costs to cross legal boundaries. Rational choice theory suggests two levels of decision. At the macro level, it consists of deciding to commit a crime or not, according to the various parameters known by the offender and the outcome of the cost-benefit analysis. At the micro level, it concerns all the decisions made by the offenders to achieve their goal (Cornish & Clarke, 1986, 1987). Research focusing on sexual crimes showed that sex offenders follow a rational choice reasoning to commit and complete their crimes (see for example Beauregard, 2005; Beauregard & Leclerc, 2007; Beauregard, Proulx, Rossmo, Leclerc, & Allaire, 2007; Beauregard, Rebocho, &

Rossmo, 2010; Beauregard, Rossmo, & Proulx, 2007; Chopin, Beauregard, Bitzer, & Reale, 2019). Led by a cost-benefit analysis, sex offenders will make a series of decisions and actions to identify and select a victim, interact with this victim, and exit the crime scene. This process is known as the modus operandi and defined as ‘the actions taken by an offender to perpetrate the offense successfully’ (Douglas, Burgess, Burgess, & Ressler, 2006, p. 353). A crucial component of the crime success is based on reducing the costs associated with the crime and consequently on the ability of offenders to avoid police detection.

Explaining the Use of Forensic Awareness Strategies

To investigate the ability of sex offenders to minimize the costs associated with the commission of their crime, previous studies used the concept of FAS. Defined for the first time by Davies (1992), the FAS concept can be described as the decisions taken by offenders to hide evidence in order to ultimately avoid apprehension. Most of empirical studies describing the use of FAS by sex offenders found that the ability to avoid police detection by sex offenders is not randomly distributed (see Beauregard & Bouchard, 2010; Beauregard & Martineau, 2012, 2018; Chopin & Beauregard, 2019b; Chopin & Beauregard, in press; Chopin, Beauregard, Gatherias, & Oliveira, 2020). Different hypotheses were formulated to explain why some sex offenders used FAS while others do not.

The Use of FAS as an Indicator of the Criminal Expertise

Criminal expertise is a multifaceted concept. It can express both criminal sophistication (i.e., well-planned crime and minimal in violence) (Beauregard & Proulx, 2017; Chopin, Paquette, & Beauregard, 2020) and offender experience (Davies, 1992). In their study, Chopin, Paquette, and colleagues (2020) defined expertise in sexual offending as the ability of offenders to demonstrate a high level of crime planning, being able to perform varied and intrusive sexual acts, while also adopting FAS. The use of FAS by offenders has been identified as an important feature of criminal expertise. Several studies suggested that

sex offenders become more forensically aware through their contact with the criminal justice system. Davies (1992) was the first to suggest that having had experience with the criminal justice system could provide offenders with education in evidentiary procedure, and the necessity to remove evidence from a crime scene (Davies, 1992). In a study based on a sample of 210 rapists, Davies, Wittebrood, and Jackson (1997) specifically analyzed their previous criminal convictions. Their findings showed that stranger rapists who took precautions to ensure their fingerprints were not left behind (e.g., using gloves) and who may have destroyed DNA evidence (e.g., by cleaning the crime scene) were respectively three and four times more likely to have been convicted for sexual offenses in the past. They also found that offenders who took precautions to remove their fingerprints were 13.39 times more likely to have had previous criminal convictions. In a study by Hazelwood and Burgess (2001), findings showed that experienced sex offenders were more often forensically aware. They explained that they used their past criminal experience to adapt their behaviors and avoid police detection (Hazelwood & Burgess, 2001). Similarly, Park, Schlesinger, Pinizzotto, and Davis (2008) found that serial rapists used more often FAS compared to non-serial rapists.

In addition to contact with the criminal justice system, some authors have also considered the role that observation could play for some offenders as a way to improve their criminal expertise. In a study focusing on child sexual abuse, Ward (1999) found that crime expertise could be learned by sex offenders through different mechanisms, such as observation and symbolic modeling (e.g., viewing of pornographic content). In the context of online sexual offending, Fortin, Paquette, and Dupont (2018) suggested that the exposure to pornography as well as networking with other offenders could provide important knowledge that could be applied to their crimes.

The Use of FAS as an Outcome of the Situational Context

It has also been suggested that based on routine activities theory (Cohen & Felson, 1979), the use of FAS by sex offenders could be strongly dependent on the situational characteristics of the crime (Beauregard & Bouchard, 2010). Situational approaches in criminology focus on criminal acts and consider that the decision-making process of offenders highly depends on the immediate circumstances surrounding their crime. As a first type of situational characteristics, previous studies investigated the influence of disinhibitory substances (i.e., alcohol and drugs) on the decision to use FAS. Davies and colleagues (1997) tested whether drug consumption could impact the decision of sex offenders to use FAS. They found that non-forensically aware rapists were more likely to have been under the influence of drugs at the time of the crime. This finding was confirmed by Beauregard and Bouchard (2010). In their study based on a sample of 72 serial rapists, they identified that the consumption of disinhibitory substances affected the decision to use FAS as offenders overlooked important details that would aid in avoiding police detection (Beauregard & Bouchard, 2010).

Another type of situational characteristics explored in empirical studies concerns the crime locations. The situational crime prevention paradigm suggests that locations strongly influence the offender behavior during the crime. These crime places can be related to the type of location (e.g., indoor location) as well as the context surrounding the crime location (e.g., deserted location). Only a few studies tested this type of situational factors associated to the use of FAS by sex offenders. Beauregard and Bouchard (2010) identified a relationship between the crime places and the use of FAS. They identified that rapists breaking and entering in the victim's residence were more often forensically aware (Beauregard & Bouchard, 2010). These findings were also confirmed by Chopin, Paquette, and colleagues (2020). They found that rapists assaulting victims in deserted and indoor locations were more likely to use strategies to avoid police detection. Chopin, Paquette, and colleagues (2020) suggested that the time spent to use FAS by sex offenders depended also on the crime place

characteristics as well as the risks of being identified. The risk of being seen or interrupted at a deserted and indoor location is usually lower, and consequently, sex offenders have more time during the crime to use FAS to avoid police detection.

Finally, Beauregard and Bouchard (2010) tested a third type of situational characteristics: victim vulnerability. They found a significant and positive relationship between the selection of a victim when she is alone (e.g., targeting a single female in their residence) and the use of FAS by rapists. However, it is important to note that this association became marginally significant once disinhibitory variables were introduced.

The Use of FAS Driven by the Crime Characteristic

Research has also shown that crime characteristics may influence the choice made by sex offenders to adopt strategies to avoid police detection. Depending on the type of acts committed during the crime, offenders may decide to spend extra time to destroy evidence left at crime scenes or flee immediately to avoid police apprehension. In their study, Chopin, Paquette, and colleagues (2020) identified that rapists committing multiple sexual acts were more likely to be forensically aware. This association can be explained by the Locard's exchange principle (Locard, 1920); the greater the number and the more intrusive (i.e., penetration) the sexual acts, the greater the intensity of the activity and thus the probability to leave evidence at the crime scene. This association was confirmed in a study by Reale, Beauregard, and Martineau (2020) who identified that SHOs perpetrating acts of sexual sadism were more often forensically aware. They also found that sadistic SHOs were more likely to act on victims and/or the environment (e.g., deactivate a home alarm, blindfold or tie up the victim), destroy and remove forensic evidence (e.g., cleaning or setting fire to the crime scene), and use other precautions such as staging the crime scene or protecting their identity (Reale and colleagues, 2020).

Aim of Study

The ability of sex offenders to avoid police detection is a central component of the modus operandi as well as in the understanding of the rational choice analysis made by offenders. Nevertheless, this aspect remains understudied, especially as data is difficult to secure for this particular aspect of the crime-commission process. Typically the information that is needed to empirically explore this question comes from various services (i.e., police data, coroner reports, forensic expertise), is confidential, and is not available for research purposes. Previous studies have shown that sex offenders do not systematically use FAS and that the decisions taken during the crime-commission process is impacted by different factors. Most of these studies concerned sexual assaults and rapes, while studies focusing on SH have been scarce. As there is no study examining the factors influencing the use of FAS by SHO, this research is exploratory and is led by two general objectives: Evaluate the prevalence in the use of FAS by SHOs and understand why some of these offenders used FAS while others did not. More specifically, we tested whether offender expertise, situational, and crime characteristics influence the use of FAS by SHOs.

Methodology

Sample

The sample used in this study was taken from the Sexual Homicide International Database (SHIELD; see Chopin & Beauregard, 2019b for a complete description of the database methodology). SHIELD includes 772 solved and unsolved cases of extrafamilial (i.e., strangers or acquaintances without familial relationships) SH from France and Canada that occurred between 1948 and 2018. Specifically, 7.09% (n = 54) of the cases occurred before 1980, 15.35% (n=117) of cases between 1980 and 1989, 32.94% (n = 251) of the cases occurred between 1990 and 1999, 35.04% (n = 267) of the cases occurred between 2000 and 2009, and 9.58% (n = 73) of the cases occurred between 2010 and 2018. SH cases were identified using the definition provided by Ressler, Burgess, and Douglas (1988), stating that

for a homicide to be considered as sexual, cases should include at least one of the following elements: (a) victim's attire or lack of attire, (b) exposure of the sexual parts of the victims body, (c) sexual positioning of the body, (d) insertion of foreign objects into the victim's cavities, (e) evidence of sexual intercourse (oral, anal, or vaginal), and (f) evidence of substitute sexual activity, interest, or sadistic fantasy. Contrary to Ressler and colleagues (1988), all cases included in SHIELD presented at least two of the criteria of the sexual homicide definition in order to minimize potential cases of false positive. Information included in the database was coded by crime analysts who examined criminal investigation files for each case. Information included in these files are mainly filled out by police officers but also by other experts involved in the investigation process (e.g., coroner, forensic psychologist, forensic experts, etc.). For the current study, a sample of 662 solved single-victim cases was selected in order to have information about the offenders.

Measure

Dependent variable. The dependent variable used in this study is dichotomous and indicates whether at least one FAS was used by SHOs during the crime (0 = no FAS used, 1 = at least one FAS was used). To create this variable we used three different types of FAS described by previous studies : The strategies consisting to protect the offender's identity, to destroy evidence and to dispose the victim's body (see e.g., Beauregard & Martineau, 2014, 2018; Chai, Beauregard, & Chopin, in press; Chopin & Beauregard, in press; Reale and colleagues, 2020). These different types of strategies were operationalized on the basis of 10 dichotomous variables (see Table 1).

Independent variables. For the independent variables, we looked at a total of 25 variables divided into three blocks: Offender expertise, situational characteristics, and crime characteristics.

Offender expertise. Several studies have suggested that the offender's expertise could explain the use of FAS by sex offenders (Davies, 1992; Davies and colleagues, 1997; Hazelwood & Burgess, 2001; Park and colleagues, 2008). In this block, we included three dichotomous variables to test the different dimensions of the concept of expertise in sexual crimes developed in the literature review (i.e., criminal experience and criminal sophistication): 1) offender had a sexual collection (i.e., pornographic movies, magazines, pictures, sexual paraphernalia), 2) offender was involved in previous criminal convictions¹, and 3) offender targeted the victim.

Situational characteristics. Previous studies have shown that the use of FAS by sex offenders can be influenced by the situation (Beauregard & Bouchard, 2010; Chopin and colleagues, 2019; Chopin, Paquette, and colleagues, 2020; Davies and colleagues, 1997). A total of 11 variables (i.e., one continuous and 10 dichotomous) were used to test different dimensions of the situational aspects of the crime (i.e., victim vulnerability, consumption of disinhibitory substances, crime location characteristics): 1) Victim age [$M = 31.41$, $SD = 18.67$], 2) victim avoided social interactions with others, 3) victim consumed alcohol prior to the crime, 4) offender consumed alcohol prior to the crime, 5) crime scene was a deserted location (i.e., no witnesses can see or interrupt the crime), 6) crime scene was the victim's residence, 7) crime scene was an outdoor location, 8) forced entry of the crime scene, 9) body recovery scene was a deserted location, 10) body recovery scene was the victim's residence, and 11) body recovery scene was an outdoor location.

Crime characteristics. Different studies showed that crime characteristics can impact the use of FAS by sex offenders (Beauregard & Field, 2008; Beauregard & Martineau, 2016; Beauregard & Proulx, 2002; Chopin, Beauregard, and colleagues, 2020; Chopin, Paquette, and colleagues, 2020; Reale and colleagues, 2020; Ressler and colleagues, 1988; Ressler,

¹ No details were available concerning previous criminal convictions

Burgess, Douglas, Hartman, & D'Agostino, 1986; Ressler, Burgess, Hartman, Douglas, & McCormack, 1986). To test this hypothesis in cases of sexual homicide, we used 10 variables (i.e., one continuous and nine dichotomous): 1) Offender used a con approach (e.g., befriended the victim, posed as an authority figure, offered assistance, etc.), 2) offender and victim were strangers (i.e., describes situations where offenders and victims were totally unknown to each other at the time of the crime), 3) number of sexual acts committed [$M = 1.69$, $SD = 1.53$], 4) vaginal penetration, 5) sexual sadism (SADSEX-SH scale was used to operationalize the concept of sexual sadism, for more details see Myers, Beauregard, & Menard, 2019)², 6) unusual acts (e.g., cannibalism, evisceration, etc.), 7) offender used restraints, 8) offender beat the victim, 9) offender stabbed the victim, and 10) offender strangled the victim.

Analytical Strategy

A two-step analytical process was followed to analyze the data. As a first step, we used bivariate analyses (i.e., chi-square, Mann-Whitney U test³) to examine the relationships between the dependent and independent variables. As a second step, we explored the differences between SHOs using FAS and those who did not. Using only the significant variables at the bivariate level, a sequential logistic regression was performed. This was done not only to better understand the impact of each variable while taking into account the other significant variables in the model, but also to identify which of the three theoretical groups of variables (i.e., offender expertise, situational characteristics and crime characteristics) was more important to explain why some SHOs used FAS. The sequential logistic regression includes three models. Model 1 includes only the offender expertise variables. Model 2 includes the offender expertise and the situational characteristics variables. Finally, Model 3

² The SADSEX-SH is a scale used to assist in the diagnostic of sexual sadism from crime scene actions.

³ We used non-parametric Mann-Whitney U test because the distribution did not follow a normal distribution.

includes all three groups of variables, namely the offender expertise, the situational characteristics, and the crime characteristics.

Results

Descriptive and Bivariate Analyses

Table 1 presents the distribution of the FAS used by SHOs. We observe that 83.99% of SHOs used at least one FAS to avoid police detection, the most common being to move the victim's body (28.55%), to conceal the victim's body (28.40%), to remove or destroy forensic evidence (27.95%), and to undress the victim's body (24.32%).

[INSERT TABLE 1 HERE PLEASE]

Table 2 presents results of the bivariate analyses between the use of FAS or not and the independent variables. SHOs that used FAS to avoid police detection were more likely to possess a sexual collection ($\chi^2 = 9.90, p < .001$), to have prior criminal convictions ($\chi^2 = 7.19, p < .010$), and to target their victim ($\chi^2 = 4.37, < .050$). Forensically aware SHOs more often selected a deserted crime location ($\chi^2 = 4.88, p < .050$) and body recovery location ($\chi^2 = 7.72, p < .010$). These SHOs also more often selected an outdoor body recovery location ($\chi^2 = 9.89, p < .001$). SHOs that did not use FAS more often selected the victim residence as the crime location ($\chi^2 = 6.60, p < .010$), and forced the entrance ($\chi^2 = 4.44, p < .050$). As for the crime characteristics, forensically aware SHOs more often perpetrated vaginal penetration ($\chi^2 = 15.68, p < .001$), sexual sadism ($\chi^2 = 21.18, p < .001$) and use of restraints ($\chi^2 = 5.76, p < .050$). SHOs using FAS perpetrated more diversified sexual acts ($U = 26306, p < .000, r = 0.11$) and were more likely to stab their victims ($\chi^2 = 4.37, p < .050$).

[INSERT TABLE 2 HERE PLEASE]

Table 3 presents findings of the binomial sequential regression examining the use or not of FAS. Model 1 includes only the variables related to the offender's expertise and presents a Nagelkerke R^2 of 0.07. Findings show that SHOs possessing a sexual collection

(OR = 3.74, $p < .010$), with prior criminal convictions (OR = 2.05, $p < .010$), and who targeted their victim (OR = 1.69, $p = .03$) were respectively 3.74, 2.05 and 1.69 times more likely to use at least one FAS. Model 2 adds situational characteristics of the crime to the offender's expertise and presents a Nagelkerke R^2 of 0.10. All the offender's expertise variables remained significant in Model 2. More specifically, when SHOs possessed a sexual collection (OR = 3.32, $p < .010$), with prior criminal convictions (OR = 2.02, $p < .010$), and targeted the victim (OR = 1.89, $p < .010$) they were respectively 3.32, 2.02 and 1.89 more likely to use at least one FAS. When SHOs forced the entry of the crime scene (OR = 1/0.60, $p < .050$) they were 1.67 times less likely to use at least one FAS. Model 3 considers offender expertise, situational characteristics, and crime characteristic variables. This model presents a Nagelkerke R^2 of 0.20. In this model, only the offender's expertise and the crime characteristics variables are significant. Cases where SHOs possessed a sexual collection (OR = 3.02, $p < .050$), with prior criminal convictions (OR = 2.01, $p < .010$), and targeted the victim (OR = 1.95, $p < .010$) were respectively 3.02, 2.01 and 1.95 more likely to use at least one FAS. Vaginal penetration (OR = 2.42, $p < .001$), sexual sadism (OR = 1.95, $p < .001$) and stabbing the victims (OR = 1.63, $p = .05$) were respectively 2.42, 1.95 and 1.63 times more likely to occur when SHOs used at least one FAS.

[INSERT TABLE 3 HERE PLEASE]

Discussion

The current study aimed to assess the prevalence of the use of FAS by SHOs and determine which factors are related to their decision to use or not FAS to avoid police detection. FAS was defined by Davies (1992) as the decisions taken by offenders to hide evidence in order to ultimately avoid apprehension. Based on previous studies (see e.g., Beauregard & Martineau, 2014, 2018; Chai and colleagues, in press; Chopin & Beauregard, in press; Reale and colleagues, 2020) we investigated three types of FAS used by SHOs to try

to avoid police detection: The protection of identity, the destruction of evidence, and the disposal of the victim's body. The protection of identity (i.e., use of condom, wore gloves) strategies are used by SHOs during the crime phase to prevent any evidence from being left at the crime scene. Our results indicate that the use of this type of strategy by SHOs is the most uncommon approach compared to other types of strategies. The destruction of evidence strategies (e.g., remove forensic evidence, etc.) seem more popular. This set of strategies is generally used by SHOs once the crime is completed. The objective of these strategies is not to avoid leaving traces of evidence, but rather to erase them once the crime is completed. Finally, the last type of strategies used by SHOs consists of disposing the victim's body (e.g., moving or concealing the victim's body), thus extending the crime scene and multiplying the potential location of traces. Chronologically, this set of measures occurs last and is used by SHOs to eliminate the major piece of evidence (i.e., the victim's body) from the crime to delay crime detection and ultimately, avoid police apprehension. Our findings show that this type of strategy is very popular for SHOs despite the fact that its use tends to increase the risk of being identified by the police (Beauregard & Martineau, 2014).

The Use of FAS by SHO: A Rational Choice Approach

Our findings showed that most SHOs used at least one FAS, while the majority used at least two different strategies to avoid police detection. We also observed that SHOs more often used FAS to destroy forensic evidence and to dispose of the victim's body. These findings are not really surprising considering that taking actions to protect their identify becomes useless in cases of SH as the victims will not be able to identify the offender after the crime. These findings are also congruent with the study by Stefanska and Carter (2019) which found that the most popular FAS used by SHOs consisted of removing evidence and disposing of the victim's body.

In their study, Beauregard and Bouchard (2010) found that more than half of rapists used at least one FAS. They hypothesized that rapists are capable of forensic awareness, but that most of them used limited and basic strategies consisting of protecting their identity. Rapists generally used strategies to protect their identity while our findings show that SHOs used FAS to remove evidence from the crime scene. From a forensic perspective, we can assume a hierarchy in the type of FAS used to avoid police detection (see Beauregard & Bouchard, 2010; Beauregard & Martineau, 2018; Chopin & Beauregard, in press; Chopin and colleagues, 2019; Chopin, Paquette, and colleagues, 2020). Strategies consisting of protecting the identity (e.g., use of condoms, gloves) can be considered as the least effective as DNA and fingerprint evidence are only useful for crime solving in situations where offenders were previously in contact with law enforcement and have their identity entered in a forensic database. DNA and fingerprint evidence can also be useful to confirm suspects identified by traditional investigative techniques and to build a case against the suspects (Baskin & Sommers, 2010). On the other hand, strategies consisting of removing evidence (i.e., cleaning or setting fire to the crime scene; disposing of the victim's body) can be considered as more effective because they follow both the objectives to avoid offender identification as well as to avoid the reconstruction of the crime. Therefore, it can be argued that SHOs are more forensically aware than rapists and two hypotheses can be suggested to explain this.

First, the fact that SHOs are more forensically aware is congruent with the rational choice approach (Cornish & Clarke, 1986, 1987). Legal and societal costs associated with the commission of a SH are higher than those associated with the commission of a rape. As opposed to rapists who sometimes mentioned a wrong assessment of the situation (e.g., not aware of the risk to be arrested, they thought that the victims consented) to explain why they did not use FAS (Beauregard & Bouchard, 2010), the presence of a dead body leads SHOs to

be more aware of the seriousness and the gravity of the situation. We can argue that the use of FAS by offenders is proportional to the seriousness of the crime.

Second, the crime-commission process involved in rape and SH presents different dynamics. In rape cases, offenders must deal with the victim release. Once the victim is no longer under the control of the offender (i.e., victim intentionally released, escaped, rescued by a third party), the risk for rapists to be arrested significantly increases. If the rapist decides to destroy forensic evidence once the crime is completed, this naturally leads to spending more time at the crime scene and consequently, increasing his exposure and his risk to be identified. A cost-benefit analysis of the situation seems to lead most rapists to escape the crime scene without using post-crime FAS. In cases of SH, the dynamic is quite different and SHOs do not have to deal with the victim release but with the victim's body instead. The immediate risk of being arrested shortly after the commission of a crime seems more limited considering the victim is no longer mobile and consequently cannot alert third parties and the police. This situation could allow SHOs to benefit from additional time before leaving the crime scene to use strategies to destroy evidence.

The Use of FAS by SHO: A Feature of Crime Expertise

As a second objective, this research aimed to explain why some SHOs used FAS and why others did not. Based on previous research findings on rapists, we tested three different hypotheses: the crime expertise, the situational characteristics, and the crime characteristics.

Multivariate results showed that both crime expertise and crime characteristics partly explained the use of FAS by SHOs, while it was not the case for situational factors. We observed that SHOs with greater criminal expertise were more likely to use FAS to avoid police detection. Included in the concept of criminal expertise are two different dimensions: offender experience and the crime sophistication.

Our findings first suggested that SHOs with previous criminal convictions were more likely to FAS to avoid police detection. This result is congruent with findings of previous studies focusing on sex offenders (Davies, 1992; Davies and colleagues, 1997; Hazelwood & Burgess, 2001; Park and colleagues, 2008). As it is the case with rapists, SHOs used their past experience with law enforcement to improve their skills to avoid police detection.

Psychosocial learning theories suggested that errors are a way of learning (see Metcalfe, 2017 for a review) and that consequently, errors committed by individuals allow them to improve their knowledge and limit the risk of repeating them. By being in contact with the criminal justice system, offenders gain insight into how a criminal investigation works and can identify errors that led to their identification the first time. The criminal justice system may educate offenders in evidentiary procedures and lead them to be more aware to remove evidence from a crime scene (Davies, 1992). We could also suggest that offenders with previous criminal convictions are more likely to be in the DNA or fingerprint database, thus potentially influencing the related FAS.

Second, our findings showed that SHOs who possessed a sexual collection (i.e., pornographic movies, magazines, pictures, sexual paraphernalia) and targeted their victims were more likely to use FAS. Both the act of targeting a victim (Beauregard & Proulx, 2017; Chopin, Paquette, and colleagues, 2020) and possessing a sexual collection (Bourke, Ward, & Rose, 2012; Ward, 1999) are considered to be characteristics of sexual offenders expertise. Beauregard and Proulx (2017) suggested that a sophisticated modus operandi is usually well-prepared and victim selection is a feature of crime anticipation and preparation. Also, Ward (1999) explained that the possession and the use of pornographic material is one of the mechanisms contributing to increase the development of expertise for sex offenders. These findings are congruent with the study by Chopin, Paquette, and colleagues (2020) which found that expert rapists are those who can combine a sophisticated modus operandi (e.g.,

strong planification, control the crime commission process) and the use of FAS. We can also noted that the combination of planning, fantasy and forethought is part of the process followed by some SHOs.

Third, findings indicate that sadistic SHOs were more likely to use FAS. This result is congruent with findings of previous studies focusing on the use of FAS by sadistic SHs (Reale and colleagues, 2020). Previous studies suggested that SHOs were less likely to use alcohol while they were more likely to have sexual convictions, to commit multiple offenses, to fantasize about their offenses (use pornography), to commit more intrusive and prolonged offenses, and to follow an organized crime-commission process (see Brittain, 1970; Chopin & Beauregard, 2019c; Hill, Habermann, Berner, & Briken, 2006; MacCulloch, Gray, & Watt, 2000; MacCulloch, Snowden, Wood, & Mills, 1983; Ressler & Burgess, 1985; Warren, Hazelwood, & Dietz, 1996). We may hypothesize that the sadistic SHOs use more often FAS as part of their planning and fantasy, as their personality traits lead to a more meticulous and controlled approach, or because they have to due to the nature of their crimes.

In line with the criminal expertise hypothesis, we can argue that SHOs who did not use FAS or who used unsophisticated FAS were novice offenders without criminal expertise (Chopin, Paquette, and colleagues, 2020). It is also plausible that SHOs who did not try to avoid police detection are those who killed the victim unintentionally (i.e., accidental killing of victims during a sexual aggression) as described in previous studies (see Chopin & Beauregard, 2019a; Stefanska & Carter, 2019). In these cases, offenders did not anticipate the lethal outcome of the crime and remained clueless on how to deal with the situation.

Situational Factors vs Crime Premeditation

Contrary to previous studies focusing on rapists' behaviors (Beauregard & Bouchard, 2010; Chopin, Paquette, and colleagues, 2020), our findings indicated that none of the 11

situational variables we tested to investigate the victim vulnerability, offender intoxication, and the crime location parameters remained significant at the multivariate level.

Consequently, these results suggest that situational characteristics of a SH do not impact the decision made by offenders to use FAS. This important but surprising result confirms that the dynamic followed by SHOs is clearly distinct from the one followed by rapists (see Beauregard, DeLisi, & Hewitt, 2018; Chopin & Beauregard, 2019d). The lack of influence of situational factors on the decision made by SHOs to use or not FAS could be explained by the level of premeditation. In the study by Healey, Beauregard, Beech, and Vettor (2016), findings showed that offenders involved in sexual crimes with a lethal outcome were more likely to premeditate their acts compared to rapists. Crime premeditation implies a better level of crime preparation. By preparing and mentalizing the crime to be committed, the offender will have time to anticipate the best options to commit their crime and use appropriate FAS to try to avoid police detection.

Our findings indicate that the crime location characteristics do not have any impact on the use of FAS. This result is contrary to the studies focusing on rapists (Beauregard & Bouchard, 2010; Chopin, Paquette, and colleagues, 2020) who identified a relationship between the crime location characteristics and the use of FAS. This difference can be explained by the fact that most of SHOs premeditated their crime and chose a location with a lower risk to be seen or interrupted by witnesses. Consequently, the hazards associated with the crime location are limited and do not impact the decision to use FAS in SH cases.

In their study, Beauregard and Bouchard (2010) highlighted the fact that alcohol consumption strongly impacted the use of FAS. They found that offenders under the influence of psychoactive substances (i.e., alcohol and/or drugs) were less forensically aware. Our findings showed that it is not the case for SHOs. Despite the fact that the majority of them consumed alcohol prior to crime commission, we can again argue that premeditation plays an

important role. Psychoactive substance consumption can have different effects on the offenders' decision-making process. Research identified that when alcohol and drugs are consumed at an appropriate dose, it can have a positive effect on the offenders' attention (see Cromwell & Olson, 2004). However, when this consumption is uncontrolled or leaves the offender too inhibited, the offender can overestimate their abilities to avoid detection or downplay risks (Assaad & Exum, 2002; Exum, 2002). We suggest that in premeditated crimes, psychoactive substance consumption contributes to the disinhibition of the homicidal fantasies of SHOs (see Chopin & Beauregard, 2019a), while in non-premeditated crimes it acts as a precipitant factor. Depending on the role of the disinhibitory substance in the crime-commission process, the level of consumption is quite different and consequently may have a different impact on the decisions taken by SHOs.

The Use of FAS and the Crime Characteristics: Counteracting the Locard's Exchange Principle?

As to the crime characteristics, our findings showed that when SHOs perpetrated vaginal penetration and sadistic sexual acts, they tended to use FAS more frequently. These findings are congruent with the studies that found greater use of FAS among sadistic SHOs as well as rapists who perpetrated a greater number of sexual acts (Chopin, Paquette, and colleagues, 2020; Reale and colleagues, 2020). According to the Locard's exchange principle (Locard, 1920), the multiplication of physical contacts (e.g., intrusive sexual acts, physical torture, etc.) increases the risk of leaving evidence at the crime scene. From a rational choice perspective, the commission of violent and intrusive sexual acts by SHOs lead them to adopt FAS to increase their chances of avoiding police detection. We suggest that depending on the type of acts committed, SHOs adapt their strategies to try to avoid police detection. According to this result, we can hypothesize that consciously or not, SHOs are aware of the link between

the type of acts committed and the risk of being identified with the evidence they left at the crime scene.

Conclusion

This research is the first to specifically focus on the factors that may have influenced SHOs to use FAS. The objective of this study was twofold: Determine the FAS used by SHOs and identify the factors leading to the decision to use it or not. Based on previous studies, we used an international database (SHIELD) and conducted multivariate analyses to determine whether criminal expertise, situational characteristics and crime characteristics could explain the differences in the use of FAS by SHOs. First, our results indicated that most SHOs used at least one FAS, while the majority of them used two or more strategies. As this study was the first to specifically investigate this question in SH cases, we compared our findings with previous studies focusing on rapists and we determined that important differences existed. Based on the rational choice approach, we argued that these differences could be explained by the level of seriousness of the crime and the socio-legal consequences incurred by SHOs: The more serious the consequences, the more likely the offenders try to avoid police detection. We also hypothesized that the different dynamics (i.e., deal the victim release vs. deal with a dead body) between rapes and SH could explain these differences in the offenders' decision-making process. Second, the comparisons of three theoretical blocks of factors showed that criminal expertise and crime characteristics are the most important factors to explain the use of FAS by SHOs, while the situational characteristics do not have any impact.

This research presents several implications. From a theoretical perspective, this research provides important findings to understand the process leading SHOs to use FAS. First, findings of this study provide the ability to determine that the decision to use FAS follows a specific logic in SH cases. Contrary to rapists, the decision to use FAS by SHOs does not seem to be influenced by situational characteristics of the crime but instead relies on

their experience, their expertise, and the type of acts they committed. These findings suggest that despite often appearing as “irrational” in terms of motivation, SH cases are committed by offenders who made rational decisions based on both the ability to maximize the benefits and avoid police detection. Criminal expertise and experience are used by SHOs to balance the maximization of benefits through the commission of intrusive and violent acts with the minimization of the costs associated with the crime-commission through the use of different types of FAS.

Another theoretical implication of the findings is related specifically to the costs/benefits analysis. While comparing the current findings with those of the previous studies on rape, it became obvious that the decision to use or not FAS was due in part to the seriousness of the crime. Once again – and compatible with a rational choice perspective – it seems that offenders involved in a SH will weight the costs and benefits of spending extra time at the crime scene to manage evidence that could link them to the crime. Most of these offenders appear to understand the consequences they face for the crime committed (e.g., a life sentence for first degree murder) if they are apprehended by the police. This perspective is very different for rapists who may consider the fact that most rapes are not reported to the police and that sentences vary greatly.

As to the practical implications, this study highlighted a link that could be established between a SHO using FAS and their previous criminal records. Specifically, the use of FAS during a SH could suggest that the wanted offender has had contact with the criminal justice system and is consequently registered in an official database. This information is important and could assist investigators in prioritizing suspects by focusing on those with previous criminal convictions.

Moreover, it is important to mention that despite SHOs adopting FAS and becoming educated as to evidentiary procedures, most of these homicides get solved by the police.

Although offenders may attempt to avoid police detection in using FAS, the police possess an arsenal of investigative tools that will counteract these detection avoidance strategies (see James & Beauregard, 2018). In many cases of unsolved crimes, it is not necessarily the actions taken by the offenders that can explain the status of the case but the actions of the police – or lack thereof – as well as the circumstances of the crime (e.g., Balemba, Beauregard, & Martineau, 2014).

Although this study provides several new findings, it is not without limitations. First, it is based on police data known to present methodological bias in terms of validity and reliability (see for example Aebi, 2006; Chopin & Aebi, 2018; Chopin & Aebi, 2019). Findings concern only cases reported by authorities and identified by researchers as SH. Based on previous findings (Aebi & Linde, 2012) we assume that the number of unreported homicides is low, but we cannot exclude that some cases of missing people could be considered as homicides. Second, in order to limit the number of false positives, cases included in SHIELD were operationalized using at least two criteria of the FBI's definition. Nevertheless, we cannot exclude that some cases with only one criterion were false negatives and consequently were not included in this study. Third, our data did not include the detailed information on the previous convictions of the offenders, making it impossible to specifically analyze this important aspect of the criminal expertise in relation to the FAS used. Fourth, this study is based on cases that occurred between 1948 and 2018. During these 70 years, investigative techniques and forensic identification have changed and evolved, which could have affected our results. However, this possibility is limited by the fact that a large portion of the cases included in this study (i.e., 48%) occurred since 2000. Fifth, we did not consider in our analysis the process of killing a victim as an avoiding detection strategy in itself while it could be the case in some SHs (Chopin & Beauregard, 2019a; Stefanska & Carter, 2019). Finally, as it was pointed out by Chopin and Beauregard (2020), the use of dichotomous

variables leads to the simplification of a complex set of interactions that constitute the criminal event and consequently limit the depth of details.

Future studies will need to investigate the concept of criminal expertise for SHOs. Specifically, research should examine which type of previous convictions impact the expertise used to avoid police detection. Further research should also focus on how the learning process works for offenders who have been in contact with the criminal justice system. Finally, qualitative studies should explore the rationale of offenders who chose not to use any FAS during the crime-commission process.

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Tables

Table 1. Descriptive analysis of FAS used by SHO (N=662)

Type of FAS		n=	% of total sample (N=662)	% of FAS users (n=547)
Protecting identity	Offender used a condom	25	3.78%	4.57%
	Offender wore gloves	20	3.02%	3.66%
Destroying evidence	Offender removed or destroyed forensic evidence	185	27.95%	33.82%
	Offender cleared scene	44	6.65%	8.04%
	Offender planted evidence/staged scene	29	4.38%	5.30%
	Offender set fire to scene	22	3.32%	4.02%
	Offender undressed victim's body	161	24.32%	29.43%
Disposing victim's body	Offender moved victim's body from the crime scene	189	28.55%	34.55%
	Offender concealed victim's body	188	28.40%	34.37%
	Offender dismembered victim's body to avoid detection	77	11.63%	14.08%
Number of FAS	0	106	16.01%	
	1	164	24.77%	29.98%
	2	148	22.36%	27.06%
	3	90	13.60%	16.45%
	4	81	12.24%	14.81%
	5	43	6.50%	7.86%
	6 and more	30	4.53%	5.48%

Table 2. Bivariate Analysis (N=662)

	No use of FAS		Use of FAS		χ^2 / Mann-Whitney <i>U</i> test
		n=115		n=547	
Offender expertise					
Offender have a sexual collection	6	5.22%	91	16.64%	9.90***
Offender involved in previous criminal conviction(s)	24	20.87%	184	33.64%	7.19**
Offender target a victim	27	23.48%	183	33.46%	4.37*
Situational characteristics					
Victim age (Mean)		33.67 [SE=20.79]		30.94 [SE=18.18]	28563.5
Offender consumed alcohol prior to crime commission	67	58.26%	303	55.39%	0.32
Victim consumed alcohol prior to crime commission	31	26.96%	140	25.59%	0.09
Victim was a loner	6	5.22%	39	7.13%	0.55
Crime scene: Deserted location	45	39.13%	276	50.46%	4.88*
Crime scene: Victim's residence	47	40.87%	157	28.70%	6.60**
Crime scene: Outdoor location	32	27.83%	202	36.93%	3.44†
Crime scene forced entry	9	7.83%	19	3.47%	4.44*
Body recovery scene: Deserted location	45	39.13%	292	53.38%	7.72**
Body recovery scene: Victim's residence	44	38.26%	136	24.86%	8.61**
Body recovery scene: Outdoor location	32	27.83%	239	43.69%	9.89***
Crime-characteristics					
Offender used con approach	58	50.43%	319	58.32%	2.41
Offender and victim are strangers	50	43.48%	265	48.45%	0.94
Number of sexual acts committed (Mean)		1.38 [SE=1.47]		1.75 [SE=1.54]	26306**
Vaginal penetration	41	35.65%	306	55.94%	15.68***
Sexual sadism [SADSEX-SH scale]	14	12.17%	185	33.82%	21.18***
Unusual acts	10	8.70%	71	12.98%	1.62
Offender used restrains	13	11.30%	115	21.02%	5.76*
Offender beat the victim	47	40.87%	251	45.89%	0.97
Offender stabbed the victim	16	13.91%	124	22.67%	4.37*
Offender strangled the victim	47	40.87%	219	40.04%	0.03

Notes. † $p \leq .1$. * $p \leq .05$. ** $p \leq .01$. *** $p \leq .001$

Table 3. Sequential binomial regression of factors predicting the use of FAS (N=662)

	Model 1			Model 2			Model 3		
	β	S.E.	Exp(β)	β	S.E.	Exp(β)	β	S.E.	Exp(β)
Offender expertise									
Offender have a sexual collection	1.32	0.44	3.74**	1.20	0.45	3.32**	1.11	0.45	3.02*
Offender involved in previous criminal conviction	0.72	0.25	2.05**	0.71	0.25	2.02**	0.70	0.26	2.01**
Offender target a victim	0.53	0.24	1.69*	0.64	0.25	1.89**	0.67	0.27	1.95**
Situational characteristics									
Crime scene: Deserted location				0.09	0.42	1.09	0.18	0.42	1.19
Crime scene: Victim's residence				0.09	0.63	1.10	0.03	0.65	1.03
Crime scene forced entry				-0.52	0.47	0.60*	-0.49	0.50	0.61
Body recovery scene: Deserted location				0.42	0.43	1.53	0.39	0.43	1.47
Body recovery scene: Victim's residence				-0.40	0.63	0.67	-0.57	0.65	0.56
Body recovery scene: Outdoor location				-0.01	0.27	0.99	-0.16	0.28	0.86
Crime characteristics									
Number of sexual acts committed							-0.03	0.09	0.97
Vaginal penetration							0.88	0.24	2.42***
Sexual sadism [SADSEX-SH scale]							1.21	0.32	3.36***
Offender used restrains							0.19	0.34	1.20
Offender stabbed the victim							0.49	0.31	1.63*
Constant	1.09	0.14	2.96***	1.19	0.23	3.30***	0.57	0.87	1.77*
χ^2	25.61***			43.64***			82.59***		
-2 log likelihood	585.72			567.69			528.74		
Cox & Snell R ²	0.04			0.06			0.12		
Nagelkerke R ²	0.07			0.10			0.20		
Overall % predicted	82.60			82.80			82.60		

Notes. *p ≤ .05. **p ≤ .01. ***p ≤ .001